

TECHNIQUE OF HIGH QUALIFICATION IN WRESTLING

Umirov Shodi Bobomurodovich

Lecturer at the Termez Institute
of Agrotechnology and innovative development
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Annotation

A highly qualified specialist in the field of Physical Education and sports should regularly increase the level of his profession. To do this, he must have the skills to carry out scientific and methodological work, be able to put research tasks ahead, choose the appropriate research methods and methods, and be able to analyze the data obtained

Key words

National wrestling, trainer, wrestling technique, training, competition, national, olympics.

A number of works are being carried out to popularize, develop and introduce the struggle to the world, which is our national sport, which in particular embodies the ideas of valor, courage, patriotism, humanism, and to transform this value into a universal masterpiece. At the same time, the growing popularity of wrestling is demanding to organize prestigious international competitions, modernize the existing infrastructure and material and technical base, improve the supply of sports inventory and clothing, expand production in this regard, and further strengthen the focus on training qualified personnel, trainers and referees for the industry.

In order to convey to future generations the rich traditions and values of the sport of wrestling inherited from our great ancestors, to increase the role of wrestling in the World Arena in the name of the Uzbek sport brand, to further strengthen the sense of patriotism in young people by supporting and encouraging their interest in national sports, to create the necessary conditions:

1. Let the following be established as the main areas of development of the national sport of wrestling (wrestling in the next places):

- wide involvement of all segments of the population in wrestling, as well as the transformation of wrestling in Uzbekistan into a nationwide sport;
- popularization of wrestling, its transformation into a masterpiece of world sport and its inclusion in the program of the International Olympic Games;
- formation of the necessary material and technical base and infrastructure to deal with the struggle;

-The inclusion of step-by-step combat and combat combat as Priority Sports in the physical training of the Armed Forces and law enforcement agencies;

-training of professional wrestling trainers, judges, development of educational and methodological manuals, strengthening the scientific and methodological base of wrestling;

- creation of the Uzbek wrestling brand, production of yaktak sportswear and wrestling carpets with the involvement of investments, implementation of measures to commercialize wrestling;

- to promote the struggle widely among the population, including through the media;

2.The Wrestling Federation of Uzbekistan, the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Tourism and sports (the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education: the Ministry),

The Ministry of finance, as well as

a) since 2021, every two years, the priority of the international competition for wrestling among students of higher education institutions is to hold international tournaments for the prize of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign countries;

b) to hold the "Uzbek polvoni" Republican competition for the struggle between employees of state bodies, institutions and organizations once a year from 2020;

c) in 2021-2025, in the Centers of the regions, in Nukus and Tashkent, the creation of fight skill schools under the Ministry (fight skill schools in the next place), which are built from light construction and materials, which are inexpensive, energy-efficient and fast-building, and are funded by state budget funds;

g) reorganization of the international wrestling Institute at the foundation of the International Wrestling Association and the Wrestling Federation of Uzbekistan;

d) consent to the proposals of the Ministry to give the specialized boarding school of the national type of wrestling of the sport, located in the Boysun District of Surkhandarya region, for free use to The Wrestling Federation of Uzbekistan, while maintaining the current financing procedure.

Since the course" types of struggle and methods of its teaching "is one of the first educational and methodological complexes created on the basis of the" methodological instruction for the preparation of new educational complexes of subjects of higher education curricula", approved by the Ministry order of March

1, 2017 No. 107, some shortcomings, controversial views and terms may occur in it. Teaching sports wrestling is a purposefully organized pedagogical process, in which the theory of sports wrestling and the knowledge of the usability of its training are aimed at forming a system of skills and qualifications, the main specific competition, refereeing, pedagogical, organizational activities of the wrestler.

The purpose of training is to form a system of knowledge that reflects the concept of the professional activity of the trainer in those involved. This concept involves the education of knowledge and skills, scientific thinking styles, a creative attitude to conscious and practical activities in those involved. The general tasks that reflect the specific conditions and characteristics of the academic discipline of sports wrestling theory and teaching equipment are as follows:

- to ensure that the knowledge of the theory and teaching equipment of the sport is of optimal size, versatility and sufficient depth;
- improving creative awareness opportunities;
- formation and improvement of the skills of the wrestler to perform general training exercises;
- methods of struggle techniques formation and improvement of the performance of defenses and countermeasures;
- formation of the optimal size and variety of technical and tactical actions in competition competitions;
- formation of skills and competencies to conduct training, training, control, competition and exhibition competitions; knowledge of the implementation of methods of struggle and the formation and improvement of skills and skills;
- show wrestling techniques and acquire explanatory skills:
- formation and improvement of knowledge, skills and skills to train and improve the performance of complex technical and tactical actions;
- formation and improvement of skills for the analysis and conduct of classes on wrestling;
- formation and improvement of knowledge, skills and skills of refereeing and organizing mass sporting events and conducting wrestling competitions.

The professional and pedagogical activity of a sports wrestling trainer is multifaceted. It includes the fulfillment of a number of obligations. Among them, the following should be distinguished: educational and educational work, management of training and competition activities of wrestlers, selection among sports-qualified and talented children, participation in scientific and

methodological work, organization and holding competitions, material and technical support of trainings and competitions, improvement of personal professional skills. The training and educational task of the trainer is considered one of the most important. It consists in the skills of training those involved in the technical and tactical actions of sports wrestling, developing physical and moral-will qualities, forming a person who has developed in every possible way.

The training task includes the skill of the trainer to show the technical movements as a pattern, to explain the exercise briefly and easily, to identify errors in the technique and its causes of occurrence, to choose the right place to observe, to analyze the technique of the exercise being performed with the student, to select preparatory movements for the method, the method and possible. It is necessary that the trainer knows how to distinguish methodical approaches to the education of physical and moral-will qualities, normalize treneriovka nagruzkas, and, depending on the individual characteristics of the trainer, choose the appropriate tools and methods:

For the targeted management of trainer athlete training, the following are:

- collect information about athletes, as well as the environment in which they live, train and compete, as well as analyze it;
- decision on athlete training strategy;
- implementation of the program and plan in practice;
- drawing up their preparation plans and programs; making changes to the training process when the training of athletes is necessary.
- control over the implementation of structured programs and plans;
- make changes to the training process if necessary.

Successful implementation of fighter training programs and plans will be possible only when the trainer is able to carry out a rational structure of the training process during the training session, working day, micro-, meso - and macrocycles, as well as a recovery consisting of pedagogical, medical-biological and mental tools and techniques will be possible only if the events are used correctly. Management of competition activities includes developing a plan for the competition competitions ahead, as well as monitoring its implementation. When developing a competition plan ahead, the trainer must have information about the opponent in order to determine the most effective tactical actions for his student to win over the opponent. Monitoring the activity of the competition and its subsequent analysis will help determine the strengths and weaknesses in the training of one or another athlete. During the competition, wrestlers are formed from the qualification of managing the activities of the competition to

observe and analyze various technical and tactical situations, as well as to make the necessary decisions in the form of certain guidelines. In the multifaceted system of training wrestlers, the task of sorting is important. He is the most talented, using various qualifying criteria for young and highly qualified athletes based on the knowledge and pedagogical experience of the trainer identification of athletes is represented by qualifications.

A highly qualified specialist in the field of physical education and sports should regularly increase the level of his profession. To do this, he must have the skills to carry out scientific and methodological work, be able to put Research tasks ahead, choose the appropriate research methods and methods, and be able to analyze the data obtained. It is necessary that the trainer knows how to organize and hold various competitions in his practical activities. To do this, he must know the rules of the type of struggle, be able to carry out arbitration duties and prepare all the necessary documents for conducting competitions. In order to structure the training process at a high level, the qualification of material and technical equipment of the training gym, equipment of the wrestling halls and the recovery center with equipment is of great importance. The effective implementation of the tasks outlined in the process of a trainer's multifaceted professional activity is determined by his love and devotion to his profession, excellent knowledge of his specialty, pedagogical abilities and a high level of personality qualities. The main way to implement this principle is to direct the practitioner to apply the acquired material in training and competition activities. It is necessary to start training in wrestling methods by introducing their use in competitions. When training in complex technical-tactical movements of wrestling, a fragmented style of training is usually used. However, if the technician involved mastered individual parts of the movement but did not know how to complete the movement, mastering individual parts of the movement in such cases would not help to occupy it entirely. The reason for such failure is that the engaged, having mastered the parts of the action, did not determine their logical connection with the task of the studied action and the purpose of the activity. The competition activity of the practitioner allows you to evaluate the results of training in movements.

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